

1 **Development of an environmentally friendly larvicidal formulation based**
2 **on essential oil compounds blend to control *Aedes aegypti* larvae:**
3 **Correlations between physico-chemical properties and insecticidal activity**

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26

27 **Abstract:**

28 Oil in water (o/w) emulsions stabilized by an amphiphilic copolymer have been studied in
29 relation to their potential insecticidal activity against *Aedes aegypti* mosquito larvae. These
30 emulsions contain as oil phase different blends of two isomeric essential oil compounds,
31 thymol and carvacrol. The results show that the addition of carvacrol facilitates the
32 dispersion of the oil within the aqueous phase, with the stabilization and polydispersity of
33 the emulsions being controlled by the change of the ratio between the copolymer
34 concentration and that of the oil phase ($R_{cop/EOC}$). Emulsions containing pure essential oil
35 compounds as oil phase do not present any significant difference on their larvicidal activity
36 against mosquito larvae, with emulsions containing only thymol being slightly more
37 effective than those containing only carvacrol as oil phase. Furthermore, the use of blends
38 containing different weight fractions of thymol and carvacrol as oil phase results in
39 formulations with an additive larvicidal activity in relation to those with the pure
40 compounds. Despite the larvicidal activity of the emulsions, they do not provoke inhibition
41 to the emergence of adult individuals in *Aedes aegypti* populations. The spreading and
42 evaporation of the emulsions onto solid surface, which may be an important parameter for
43 the performance of larvicidal formulations, was found to be dependent on the same
44 parameters that govern the stability of the emulsions. This study helps on seeking new
45 alternatives for the preparation of new eco-sustainable formulations against insect pest.

46 **Keywords:** emulsions; essential oils; insect pest control; isomers, thymol; carvacrol;
47 larvicidal

48 **Introduction**

49 The biological properties of essential oils (EOs),¹⁻⁴ and their classification as GRAS
50 (Generally Recognized As Safe) products with a reduced impact on environment and health,⁵
51 have led to an increasing interest for their potential use in several fields, from cosmetics to
52 food science and from pharmaceuticals to agriculture.⁶⁻⁹ However, the inclusion of EOs in
53 consumer products remain rather limited yet due to their volatility, thermal lability, poor
54 water solubility, and stability, which are important drawbacks for the manipulation and
55 handling of these compounds^{10,11}. Therefore, it is necessary to design appropriate strategies
56 for taking advantage of the EOs biological activity on the manufacturing of new eco-
57 sustainable products¹²⁻¹⁴.

58 Seeking new strategies for the manipulation and use of essential oils in commercial
59 formulations, the use of encapsulation procedures is a promising alternative to reduce the
60 volatility of the EOs, improve their dispersion in water and enhance their availability^{6, 15-22}.
61 This can be easily done by using oil-in-water (o/w) emulsions, that is a widely extended
62 method for the design of formulations in many industrial processes²³⁻²⁵. This route enabling
63 an easier handling of essential oils can be exploited on the preparation of new formulations
64 of botanical insecticides with low impact for environment and non-target organisms.²⁶⁻²⁹

65 Different studies have shown that the inclusion of EOs within the oil phase of o/w emulsions
66 (alone or combined with an organic solvent) presents a significant impact against different
67 insect pests. A dose dependent larvicidal activity against *Aedes aegypti* larvae was reported
68 for nanoemulsions of *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. and *Ocimum basilicum* L. oils^{30,31}, with the
69 susceptibility of the larvae being stronger than essential oil incorporated within the oil phase
70 the emulsion than the free form³². Similar results were found upon the exposure of *Culex*
71 *quinquefasciatus* to eucalyptol, with the time required to obtain a 100% of mortality being
72 reduced 6-fold when insects are exposed to emulsions in relation to the exposure to the same
73 dose of the free essential oil³³. Furthermore, the size of the oil droplets was found to be a
74 critical parameter on the modulation of the bio-toxicity of the formulations, the smaller the
75 droplets the higher the mortality is³⁴. Similar impact of the droplet size on the biological
76 activity of different nanoemulsions against *Rhopalosiphum padi* has been also reported
77 recently by Pascual-Villalobos et al.³⁵

78 It is worth mentioning that most of the studies related to emulsions containing EOs for insect
79 pest control explore the impact of the whole EO on the insecticidal activity of the

80 formulations^{36, 37}, and scarce data are available about the utility of individual essential oil
81 compounds or their mixtures against insect pest. It is know that the combination of several
82 EO compounds may result in an enhanced bio-toxicity of the formulations against specific
83 insect pest, even though the mechanisms of this synergism are not clear yet³⁸⁻⁴⁰. Similar
84 results have been found by adding a second essential oil compound (thymol) to o/w emulsions
85 containing eugenol, with the larvicidal activity against *Aedes aegypti* larvae of such
86 dispersion being significantly enhanced as the concentration of the second component is
87 increased.⁴¹ These results opened new perspectives on the development of new botanical-
88 derived larvicidal formulations against mosquitos. It is worth mentioning that even though
89 the use of commercial insecticides, many of them as emulsifiable concentrates, including
90 essential oils for pest management has undergone a moderate growth in recent years,
91 especially in the USA and the EU,²⁶ none of these products have been tested as mosquito
92 larvicidal, in spite of a great deal of research in this direction.⁴² This may be associated with
93 a potential toxicity against non-target aquatic organisms which is a barrier to regulatory
94 approval of the use of these products. Thus, it is necessary to seek new alternatives for taking
95 advantage of the toxicity of essential oils against insect larvae, minimizing the potential risks
96 for environment and non-targeted organism, which is only possible by a careful examination
97 of the stabilizing molecules and by the minimization of the use of organic solvents to vehicle
98 the essential oil. These aspects are addressed in this work, where essential oils compounds
99 are directly incorporated as the oil phase of the emulsions, without any additional organic
100 solvent for their dispersion within the formulation. Furthermore, the use of an emulsifying
101 molecule with low toxicity such as the amphiphilic triblock copolymer Pluronic[®] F127 favors
102 the minimization of environmental risks.⁴³ Pluronic[®] F127 is a triblock copolymer with two
103 lateral blocks of poly(ethylene-glycol) and a central one of poly(propylene-glycol), enabling
104 the dispersion of essential oil compounds within the hydrophobic region of the
105 supramolecular aggregates formed by such polymer in aqueous solution.

106 This work analyzes the effect of the nature of the oil phase, formed by different blends of
107 carvacrol and thymol (positional isomers, see Scheme 1 for their molecular structures), on
108 the larvicidal activity of o/w emulsions stabilized by Pluronic[®] F127 against *Aedes aegypti*
109 larvae. It is worth mentioning that the similarity of thymol and carvacrol may not be
110 correlated to their biological activity, as it was reported in previous studies for their respective
111 activity against *Pediculus humanus capitis*⁴⁴ or their anti-microbial properties⁴⁵. Therefore,
112 it should be expected that the biological activity of their mixtures cannot be to be rationalized
113 in terms of the behavior of the pure components.

114

115 **Scheme 1.** Molecular structures for thymol (left) and carvacrol (right).

116

117 It is expected that this work can be useful as a preliminary step towards the fabrication of
118 new more eco-friendly formulations for insect pest control, that further have reduced health
119 impact. In this work we will take advantage of the stabilization and ease of the dispersion
120 process of essential oil compound drops in water provided by the eco-friendly surfactant
121 character of the Pluronic[®] F127 copolymer⁴⁴. This allows preparing the formulations *in situ*
122 which may contribute to a significant reduction of the economic costs and pollutant emissions
123 associated with the transport of large amounts of aqueous formulations from factory to the
124 application place, helping on the minimization of the CO₂ footprint.

125

126 **Materials and Methods**

127 **Chemicals**

128 Thymol (2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenol) and carvacrol (5-Isopropyl-2-methylphenol) with
129 purities $\geq 99\%$ were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, MO, USA). Pluronic[®] F127
130 was also purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, MO, USA). Pluronic[®] F127 is a
131 triblock copolymer which presents a molecular weight of 12.600 kDa (4.4 kDa for each
132 poly(ethylene-oxide) and 3.8 kDa for the central poly(propylene-oxide), i.e. 101 and 56
133 monomers, respectively). All the chemicals were used as received without further
134 purification.

135 Ultrapure deionized water used for cleaning and preparation of the dispersions was
136 obtained by a multicartridge purification system AquaMAX™-Ultra 370 Series. (Young
137 Lin Instrument Co., Ltd., Gyeonggi-do, South Korea), with a resistivity higher than 18
138 MΩ·cm, and a total organic content lower than 6 ppm.

139 **Preparation of emulsions stabilized by Pluronic® F127**

140 The samples were prepared in tubular glass vials (10 mL) following a procedure adapted
141 from our previous publication.⁴⁴ Briefly, it consists in the initial addition of weighted
142 amounts of a stock aqueous solution of Pluronic® F127 (concentration 10 wt%) in the vial,
143 followed by the pouring of weighted amounts of thymol and carvacrol to obtain final mixtures
144 with a total concentration of oil phase (essential oil compounds blend) within the 1-5 wt%
145 range and different thymol:carvacrol weight ratios. Afterwards the mixtures are then diluted
146 with ultrapure water to obtain the final mixtures, with a Pluronic® F127 concentration (C_{cop})
147 composition in the 1-7.5 wt% range. Once all the components have been added, the mixtures
148 are homogenized using a magnetic stirrer (1000 rpm) at 70 °C during 5 hours. This heating
149 is important because thymol is a solid compound (melting point around 50°C), and their
150 incorporation within the oil phase of the emulsions is facilitated by the increase of the
151 temperature. Once the final liquid mixtures are obtained, they are cool down and left to age
152 during 1 week before using them to perform any physico-chemical or biological test.

153 **Characterization of the dispersions**

154 The determination of the compositional ranges, in which emulsions remain stable during at
155 least six month (microemulsions or nanoemulsions), was performed at a temperature of 25
156 °C for mixtures containing different thymol:carvacrol weight ratios. This type of studies
157 allows mapping the compositional regions in which pseudo-single phase mixtures with
158 potential utility in the fabrication of new botanical insecticides may be prepared.

159 **Dynamic Light Scattering**

160 Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) experiments were carried out using a Zetasizer Nano ZS
161 (Malvern Instruments Ltd., United Kingdom) in quasi-backscattering configuration
162 (scattering angle, $\theta = 173^\circ$) using the radiation from the red line of a He-Ne laser (wavelength,
163 $\lambda = 632$ nm). DLS experiments provides information of the characteristic diffusion time of
164 Brownian scatters τ at fixed temperature (25°C in our studies) which is related to the apparent
165 diffusion coefficient D_{app} of such scatters^{46, 47}

166 $\frac{1}{\tau} = D_{app} q^2,$ (1)

167 where $q = (4\pi n / \lambda) \sin(\theta / 2)$ is the wavevector, n the refractive index of the continuous
168 phase. The values of D_{app} allow one to estimate the apparent hydrodynamic diameter of the
169 scatters, d_h^{app} , through the Stokes-Einstein equation

$$d_h^{app} = \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta D_{app}}, \quad (2)$$

170 where k_B and T are the Boltzmann constant and the absolute temperature, respectively, and η
171 is the viscosity of the solvent. It is worth mentioning that the aforementioned DLS technique
172 can be only used on the analysis of transparent dispersions.

173 **Spreading and evaporation of emulsion microdroplets**

174 Measurements of the contact angle of emulsion microdroplets (2-4 μL) deposited onto silicon
175 wafers (Siltronix, Archamps, France) using a Hamilton microliter syringe (SN 701, 10 μL)
176 were performed using a set-up consisting on a cylindrical steel chamber (13 cm of diameter,
177 10 cm of depth) fitted with flat glass windows on the side and at the bottom positioned in
178 such a way that allow one to follow the time evolution of the droplet contour^{48,49}. The images
179 of the drop shape were captured using a CCD camera (KODAK IT CCD KAI340), at a
180 maximum rate of 60 frames per second with a 640 x 480 pixels resolution. The temperature
181 of the measuring chamber was controlled at $25.0 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$.

182 The images of the sessile droplets were analyzed according to the axisymmetric drop shape
183 analysis profile (ADSA-P) method⁵⁰ allowing one to obtain the contact diameter, $2L$, and its
184 height h . This allows estimating the contact angle θ and the volume V of the sessile droplet
185 assuming that it has a spherical-cap shape

186 $\frac{\theta}{2} = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{h}{L}\right),$ (3)

187 and

188
$$V = \frac{\left[\frac{\pi}{3} (L)^3 \right] (1 - \cos \theta)^2 (2 + \cos \theta)}{\sin^3 \theta}. \quad (4)$$

189 **Insecticidal activity of the dispersions**

190 **Larvicidal bioassays**

191 A colony of *Aedes aegypti* (Rockefeller Strain, Venezuela), maintained in a bioterium of
192 PIET-INEDES (CONICET-UNLu) from 2018 at 25±1°C, 65-80 % of Relative Humidity
193 (RH), and a L12/D12 photoperiod (exposure to alternate 12 hours periods of light and
194 darkness) and free of exposure to pathogens, insecticides, or repellents, was used for
195 larvicidal bioassays⁵¹. These involves the addition of different volumes (0.05 to 2 mL) of the
196 tested emulsions to drinking water up to a final volume of 225 mL (final emulsion
197 concentration within 1-250 ppm range), followed by the addition of 25 mL of water
198 containing 20 late third-instar or early four-instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti* into the container.
199 Control experiments were performed following the same procedure described above,
200 replacing the emulsions by a Pluronic® F127 aqueous solutions (concentration 10 wt%). Food
201 supply was offered to larvae and the larval mortality was recorded after 24 h of exposure⁴¹.

202 The mortality was assumed for those insects which failed to move, were unable to rise to the
203 surface within a 1 min or does not evidence the characteristic diving reaction when the water
204 is disturbed⁵². The percentage of larvae affected or the degree of mortality was determined,
205 and a Probit analysis was performed to estimate lethal concentration affecting to the 50% of
206 the individuals (LC₅₀)⁵³. Lethal concentrations (LCs) correspond to the concentrations of
207 thymol, eugenol or their mixtures dispersed in the emulsions and are expressed as parts per
208 million in the final mixture (ppm). Four replicates were performed of each experiment, and
209 the percentage of mortality (%) was obtained as the average value. Furthermore, the effective
210 concentration required for the reduction of the emergence of adult individuals by 50% , i.e.
211 the median *emergence inhibition* (EI₅₀), was evaluated as the last specimen of the
212 experimental group that emerged or died. This was done in experiments in which 5 mg of
213 larval food were added to the container with the diluted emulsion after 24 hours of exposure.

214 The food supply was maintained until more than 90% of the control mosquitoes emerge or
215 die, with the latter being evaluated. Mortality data were corrected using Abbott's formula
216 when the mortality ranged between 10-20% of the insects tested in control groups.⁵⁴ Note
217 that values of mortality below 10% of the insects tested were assumed within the natural
218 variability.

219 The data were processed using the PoloPlus v.2.0 software (LeOra Software, Berkley,
220 California, United States of America) and the values were considered statistically significant
221 when the 95% confidence limits did not overlap. Drinking water quality was analyzed by
222 Química MATCO (Luján, Buenos Aires, Argentina) and the results were the following:

223 Drinking water composition (mg/mL): alkalinity 399, chloride 35, calcium 66.7, magnesium
224 51, total hardness (CaCO₃) 37, dissolved oxygen < 0.20, nitrate < 5, sulfate 41.5, nitrite <0.01
225 and residual chlorine 0. Conductivity (μS/cm): 1058. pH: 7.84.

226 **Biological interactions between thymol and carvacrol**

227 The interaction between thymol and carvacrol in the blends containing different
228 thymol:carvacrol ratios (1:0; 0.75:0.25; 0.50:0.50; 0.25:0.75 and 0:1) was evaluated by the
229 comparison of the expected value of LC₅₀ and that obtained experimentally: $R = LC_{50}$
230 $\text{expected} / LC_{50} \text{ experimental}$. The expected values were determined based on Wadley's
231 calculation as ⁵⁵

$$232 \text{ expected } LC_{50} = \frac{x_t + x_c}{\frac{x_t}{LC_{50}^t} + \frac{x_c}{LC_{50}^c}}, \quad (5)$$

233 where x_t and x_c represent the weight fractions of thymol and carvacrol in the mixture,
234 respectively, and LC_{50}^t and LC_{50}^c are the values of LC₅₀ for pure thymol and pure carvacrol,
235 respectively. Thus, according to Wadley ⁵⁵ it is possible to assume that $R > 1.5$ indicates
236 synergistic interaction; $1.5 \geq R > 0.5$ appears for additive interactions and $R \leq 0.5$ evidences
237 an antagonistic interaction.

238

239 **Results**

240 **Determination of the stability regions for essential oil in water emulsions**

241 An important preliminary step on the design of formulations of o/w emulsions with potential
242 application in pest control is the evaluation of the stability regions for the studied pseudo-
243 ternary mixtures (water/essential oil compounds/copolymer), i.e. the definition of the
244 compositional regions within emulsions are obtained. Figure 1 shows the compositional maps
245 for the two pseudo-ternary mixtures in which the oil phases are formed for the pure EOs
246 (thymol or carvacrol) and for a mixture with an oil phase formed by a equimolar blend of
247 both essential oil compounds (thymol:carvacrol ratio 0.5:0.5).

248 The analysis of the compositional maps obtained for the pseudo-ternary system evidences
249 the existence of at least three different types of mixtures within the explored composition
250 ranges: (i) phase separated mixtures, (ii) opalescent emulsions and (iii) transparent
251 emulsions. The transition from phase separated mixtures to transparent emulsions, passing
252 through the compositional range corresponding to opalescent emulsions, appears with the
253 increase of the ratio between the concentration of the copolymer (Pluronic[®] F127) and the
254 concentration of the essential oil compound in the pseudo-ternary mixtures, $R_{cop/EOC}$. This
255 suggests the existence of a minimum concentration of copolymer below which it is not
256 possible to accomodate all the essential oil compound within the hydrophobic environment
257 of the emulsion, resulting in the phase separation of the mixtures. Similar conclusions are
258 obtained from the evaluation of the emulsions containing 0.75:0.25 and 0.25:0.75
259 thymol:cavacrol ratios.

260

261 Figure 1. Compositional maps for the different pseudo-ternary mixtures (water/essential oil
 262 compound/copolymer) represented as the dependence of the oil phase concentration on the
 263 Pluronic® F127 concentration (c_{cop}): (a) Mixtures with thymol as oil phase. (b) Mixtures with
 264 carvacrol as oil phase (c) Mixtures with an equimolar thymol:carvacrol blend as oil phase
 265 (thymol:carvacrol ratio 0.5:0.5). In the three panels: (■) Phase-separated mixtures. (▲)
 266 Opalescent emulsions. (●) Transparent emulsions.

267

268 The examination of the three compositional maps shows that the replacement of thymol for
 269 carvacrol in the oil phase of the pseudo-ternary mixtures results in an enhanced dispersion of
 270 the oil within the aqueous continuous phase, i.e. higher amounts of essential oil compounds
 271 may be dispersed for a fixed amount of copolymer without any signature of phase separation.
 272 This suggests that carvacrol plays an important role for improving the solubilization of the
 273 solid thymol (melting point around 50 °C) within the oil phase, enhancing its dispersion

274 within the aqueous medium. The worst capacity of the copolymer for dispersing thymol than
275 carvacrol is clear from the threshold values of $R_{cop/EOC}$ above which the phase separation
276 occurs in each system. This value is above 0.5 and 0.6 for emulsions with thymol and
277 carvacrol as oil, respectively. This may present a critical impact in the further development
278 of these type of systems for the solubilization and distribution of other bioactive molecules.

279 **Determination of the sizes of the droplets for essential oil compounds in water** 280 **emulsions**

281 The size of the emulsions belonging to the compositional region in which transparent
282 emulsions are formed may be estimated from DLS measurements in terms of the apparent
283 hydrodynamic diameter d_H^{app} . The evaluation of the size of the droplets presents a key
284 importance when systems for pest control are considered, mainly because an enhanced
285 penetration of the formulation through the insect cuticle and consequently a higher toxicity
286 of the formulations may be expected as the average size of the droplets is reduced^{34,35}. Figure
287 2a shows, for the sake of example, the intensity auto-correlation functions obtained for
288 transparent emulsions containing a fixed amount of carvacrol as oil-phase and increasing
289 copolymer concentrations.

290 The intensity auto-correlation functions shift to smaller relaxation times with the increase of
291 the copolymer concentration, which is ascribed to a decrease of the average size of the
292 droplets. However, the clear bimodal character of the intensity auto-correlation functions
293 found for most of the explored mixtures (only emulsions with the highest values of $R_{cop/EOC}$
294 appear as mono-modal) makes it difficult to obtain an evaluation of the size of the droplets
295 from the time-scale within the auto-correlation function decay. Therefore, the bimodal
296 character of the intensity auto-correlation functions is a signature of polydispersity. It is worth
297 mentioning that the decrease of the copolymer concentration makes the intensity
298 autocorrelation more clearly bimodal. This is explained assuming that the dispersion of
299 essential oils droplets in water requires a minimum amount of copolymer to ensure the
300 formation of a shell with a hydrophobic pool, thus enabling the distribution of the essential
301 oil, and giving stability to the droplets^{56, 57}. However, the decrease of the copolymer

302 concentration leads to a situation in which the number of molecules is not enough to stabilize
303 monodisperse emulsions with small droplets, thus the droplets start to coalesce which results
304 in an increase of the average size of the droplets and, hence, the polydispersity of the
305 emulsions. The increase of the average size of the droplets allows a minimization of the area
306 of the interface between the droplets and the continuous phase, and matter of fact reduces the
307 amount of copolymer required for coating the droplets. The limit case of this phenomena is
308 the onset of the compositional region in which opalescent emulsions are formed, and after a
309 further decrease of the copolymer concentration the emergence of the phase separation region
310 (see Figure 1). It is worth noting that DLS does not allow investigating the two latter systems.
311 Even though, the above discussion has been focused in emulsions containing only carvacrol
312 on the oil phase, similar results were found independently of the composition of the essential
313 oil compounds blend forming the oil phase (see insets of Figure 2 for the case of emulsions
314 containing an equimolar blend of thymol and carvacrol as oil phase).

315 The bimodal character of the auto-correlation function results is also evidenced from the
316 distributions of the apparent hydrodynamic diameters shown in Figure 2b. Such distributions
317 show, for most of the copolymer concentrations, two separated distributions, the first one
318 corresponding to droplets with an average diameter in the 25-75 nm range and the second
319 containing droplets with an average apparent hydrodynamic diameter more than one order of
320 magnitude larger. It is worth mentioning that the droplets with the smallest size correspond
321 to the most important contribution, which is explained considering that the scattered intensity
322 increases by a 10^6 factor with the size of the scatters, thus the population having the most
323 significant contribution in the distribution may not correspond to that involving the highest
324 number of scatters ^{46, 47}.

325

326 Figure 2. Intensity auto-correlation functions (a) and d_h^{app} distributions (b) for emulsions with
 327 a fixed carvacrol concentration (1 wt%) and different Pluronic[®] F127 concentrations (c_{cop}).
 328 The data corresponds to emulsions in which the oil phase is pure carvacrol. The insets
 329 corresponds to the same results shown in the main panels for emulsions in which the oil phase
 330 is formed by equimolar blend of thymol and carvacrol (thymol:carvacrol ratio 0.5:0.5).

331

332 A detailed analysis of the distributions points out that the smallest droplets decrease their size
 333 as c_{cop} increases, whereas the opposite is true for the droplets with the highest sizes.
 334 Furthermore, the contribution associated with the smallest droplets becomes more important
 335 with the increase of c_{cop} , whereas the second contribution decrease its importance until its
 336 complete disappearance for the highest copolymer concentrations. This confirms again the
 337 aforementioned importance of a minimal copolymer concentration for preventing the
 338 destabilization processes which result in an increase of the sizes of the droplet and
 339 polydispersity. Thus, the increase of the size of the biggest droplets until its disappearance
 340 for the highest copolymer concentration can be considered as a signature of a destabilization
 341 by Ostwald ripening. This is rationalized assuming that the decrease of the size of the smallest
 342 droplets with the increase of the copolymer concentration results from the availability of
 343 higher amounts of copolymer to coat larger interfacial areas, providing the bases for the
 344 reduction of the average size of the droplets. Furthermore, the decrease of the size of the
 345 smallest droplets leads to an increase of the internal pressure differences between big and

346 small droplets which drives to the Ostwald ripening, and the growing of the biggest droplets
347 following process. However, the contribution associated with the biggest droplets reduces its
348 importance with the increase of the polymer concentration, disappearing for the highest
349 copolymer concentrations. This is explained considering that the increase of the polymer
350 availability leads to an increase of the stabilization of the droplets, i.e. the coating is strong
351 enough to reduce the impact of the Ostwald ripening. Notice that the increase of importance
352 of the low-size contribution indicates that the ratio between the number of small and large
353 droplets increases steeply, which may affect to the bioactivity of the formulations.

354 The above discussion corresponds to the impact of the copolymer on the stabilization of the
355 emulsions. However, another important parameter is the amount of oil incorporated within
356 the emulsion. This requires an analysis of the effect of the oil concentration on the size of the
357 droplets for a fixed copolymer concentration. Figure 3 shows the intensity auto-correlation
358 function for emulsions with a fixed concentration of copolymer and different carvacrol
359 concentrations. The results show again the importance of the $R_{cop/EOC}$ value on the
360 stabilization of the emulsion droplets, with the polydispersity of the emulsions, evidenced
361 from the intensity auto-correlation function and the size distribution, being reduced as the
362 amount of available copolymer increases.

363 This work is focused on the study of the larvicidal activity of emulsions containing as oil
364 phase different essential oil compounds blends, this makes it interesting to evaluate the
365 impact of the composition of the oil phase on the dispersion of the oil. Figure 4a and 4b shows
366 the intensity auto-correlation functions and the d_h^{app} distributions, respectively, for emulsions
367 containing different essential oil blends as oil phase in which the concentrations of copolymer
368 and essential oil are maintained constant. The intensity-autocorrelation functions does not
369 evidence any significant difference on the character of the obtained dispersions, appearing
370 independently of the nature of the oil phase a bimodal decay. However, the differences as
371 function of the composition of the essential oil blend are more evident from the d_h^{app}
372 distributions (see Figure 4b). It is true that it is not easy to obtain an evaluation of the average
373 sizes corresponding to small and big droplets because they start to be coupled as the thymol

374 concentration is increased (lower values of x_c). However, the clearer separation of the
375 populations corresponding to the droplets having different sizes as carvacrol content
376 increases suggests a better dispersion of the thymol within the hydrophobic shell formed for
377 the copolymer and, consequently, it would possible possible to assume that the higher the
378 concentration of carvacrol in the oil phase the better the dispersion of the essential oil within
379 the aqueous phase is. This confirms the picture obtained from the compositional maps shown
380 in Figure 1, with the increase of the carvacrol concentration leading to an increase of the
381 amount of oil that can be distributed in the aqueous phase without the aqueous continuous
382 phase. This agrees with previous results for o/w emulsions stabilized with Pluronic® F127
383 using blends of thymol and eugenol as oil phase ⁴¹.

384

385 Figure 3. Intensity auto-correlation functions for emulsions, in which the oil phase is
386 carvacrol, with a fixed Pluronic® F127 concentration (7.5 wt%) and two different carvacrol
387 concentrations. The inset shows the d_H^{app} distributions corresponding to the samples on the
388 main panel.

389

390

391 Figure 4. (a) Intensity auto-correlation functions for emulsions with different essential oil
 392 blends as oil phase (indicated by the weight fraction of carvacrol x_c), and fixed Pluronic[®]
 393 F127 (3.25 wt%) and essential oil compounds (1 wt%) concentration. (b) d_h^{app} distributions
 394 for selected emulsions with different essential oil blends as oil phase (indicated by the weight
 395 fraction of carvacrol x_c), and fixed Pluronic[®] F127 (3.25 wt%) and essential oil compounds
 396 (1 wt%) concentrations.

397

398 Larvicidal activity of essential oil in water emulsions against *Aedes aegypti* larvae

399 The larvicidal activity of different transparent emulsions presenting thymol:carvacrol blends
 400 with different ratios between the essential oil compounds forming the oil phase, and a fixed
 401 copolymer (5 wt%) and total essential oil compounds (1.25 wt%) concentrations was
 402 evaluated in terms of the lethal concentration affecting 50% of the exposed larvae (LC₅₀) and
 403 the effective concentration to reduce adult emergence by 50% (EI₅₀), with both being
 404 calculated by Probit analysis with an overlapping of the confidence intervals of 95%. Figure
 405 5 shows the values of the values of LC₅₀ and EI₅₀ as function of the fraction of carvacrol in
 406 the oil phase, x_c .

407 The tested emulsions results, in all the cases, in acute toxicity in mosquito larvae, although
 408 significant differences exist on their toxicity depending on the composition of the oil phase.
 409 Emulsions containing only thymol in the oil phase present the highest larvicidal activity

410 against *Aedes aegypti* larvae, which is worsened as carvacrol is introduced within the oil
 411 phase, i.e. emulsions containing thymol:carvacrol blends as oil phase presents a worst
 412 larvicidal activity than when thymol is the only component of the oil phase. Nevertheless,
 413 the larvicidal activity of emulsions containing only carvacrol is not significant different to
 414 those containing only thymol. On the other hand, the use of thymol:carvacrol blends to
 415 substitute the thymol from the oil phase results in a reduction on the larvicidal activity of the
 416 emulsions. It is worth noting that even though there are no significant differences between
 417 the emulsions of the pure compounds, those containing only thymol as oil phase present
 418 significant differences in their activity with respect to emulsions containing thymol:carvacrol
 419 blends as oil phase. However, the differences on the activity of emulsions containing only
 420 carvacrol and those containing essential oil compound blends as oil phase are not significant.

421
 422 Figure 5. Larvicidal activity of emulsions of thymol, carvacrol and their mixtures against
 423 larvae of *Aedes aegypti*. Each bar represents the LC_{50} (a) and the EI_{50} (b) values obtained by
 424 probit analysis on the carvacrol fraction contained in the oil phase (all the emulsions present
 425 a copolymer and total essential oil compounds concentrations of 5 wt% and 1.25 wt%,
 426 respectively). The error bars indicate the variability of the data, with the average values of
 427 LC_{50} and EI_{50} being obtained by Probit analysis with an overlapping of the confidence
 428 interval of 95%. The symbols (■) in the panel a correspond to the values obtained for the
 429 expected LC_{50} calculated according the Wadley's calculation represented by equation (5) and

430 the line is a guide for the eyes. The lowercase letters above each bar evidence the significance
431 in the difference between the results obtained for the different formulations, with the same
432 letters indicating the absence of significant differences between treatments. The number
433 larvae tested for each formulations was 480.

434

435 It is true that the toxicity of the essential oil compounds dispersed in the emulsions against
436 *Aedes aegypti* larvae is around five orders of magnitude lower than that of the synthetic
437 insecticide pyriproxyfen or one thousand times lower than that corresponding to the spinosad
438 ⁵⁸. However, the dispersion of essential oil compounds as the oil phase of o/w emulsions
439 leads to a larvicidal activity several times higher than that reported for free essential oils ⁵⁹.
440 Therefore, even though emulsions containing essential oils are less effective than most of the
441 commonly used synthetic insecticides, they may be considered as promising tools in the
442 design of new formulations for eco-sustainable botanical insecticides ²⁶. It must be stressed
443 that it is always possible to include pyriproxyfen, or another synthetic insecticide, in the oil
444 droplets to increase its activity, but containing a smaller amount of insecticide than that
445 corresponding to the normal application dose of the insecticide, thus making the formulation
446 less eco-aggressive. Furthermore, the substitution of the flammable organic solvents (xylene,
447 toluene or gas-oil) commonly used in pesticide manufacturing by oily derivatives of essential
448 oils would make it possible to reduce the risks associated with the manufacturing and use of
449 insecticidal products.

450 The above results allow one to evaluate the interactions occurring between thymol and
451 carvacrol in their blends, which was found additive (R values in the 0.6-0.7 range for all the
452 studied emulsions) in agreement with the results by Youssefi et al.⁶⁰ for the activity of
453 thymol:carvacrol mixtures against eggs of *Culex pipiens*. However, this additive effect
454 contrasts with the synergetic activity of thymol and carvacrol against *Culex pipiens* larvae ⁶⁰,
455 *Dermanyssus gallinae* ⁶¹, *Dermacentor nitens* ⁶², *Amblyomma sculptum* ⁶², *Rhipicephalus*
456 (*Boophilus*) *microplus* and *Rhipicephalus sanguineus* ⁴⁰, and the antagonistic interaction
457 found against *Drosophila melanogaster* ⁶³. Furthermore, the comparison of thymol:carvacrol

458 and thymol:eugenol⁴¹ mixtures show significant differences, with the latter evidencing an
459 antagonistic interaction between the components. Thus, the results suggest that chemical
460 similarity between thymol and carvacrol presents a certain role on the interactions occurring
461 between the components.

462 The IE₅₀ values do not show any significant difference with those obtained for the LC₅₀.
463 Therefore, it is possible to assume the absence of any significant impact of the emulsions on
464 the growth of the remaining *Aedes aegypti* larvae, and consequently no inhibition of adult
465 emergence in addition to larvae mortality was found after 24 hours of exposure. Thus,
466 emulsions present an initial acute toxicity of larvae, without any subsequent sublethal effect
467 on emergence of adult individuals. Therefore, these results suggest that within the
468 concentration range studied, the emulsions do not present any pupicidal activity, which may
469 be explained considering the higher resistance of pupae than larvae (LC₅₀ has been reported
470 to be between 10 and 100 fold higher for pupae than for larvae ⁶⁴). It is worth mentioning
471 that the LC₅₀ of Pluronic[®] F127 required for producing mortality on pupae was found around
472 a value of 570 ppm,⁴⁴ which is a value one order of magnitude higher than the corresponding
473 to the LC₅₀ reported here for the emulsions.

474 The above discussion suggests that the organization of the essential oil within the emulsions
475 or the size of the droplets do not play a significant role on the toxicity of the here studied
476 thymol:carvacrol blends in water emulsions, with the chemical nature of the oil phase being
477 probably the most critical role. This can be explained considering that even though the
478 polydispersity of the different tested formulations may be very different, the average size of
479 the smaller droplets is very similar independently of the essential oil compound blend
480 included within the emulsion. Therefore, the results suggest that the specific nature of the oil
481 phase may be a parameter with a stronger impact on the biological activity of the emulsions
482 than the differences on the droplets concentration.

483 **Spreading and evaporation of essential oil in water emulsions onto solid surface**

484 The evaluation of the spreading and evaporation of microdroplets upon their deposition onto
485 solid surfaces present interest on the design of formulations for pest control because these
486 phenomena may contribute to the distribution on the formulations within the environment
487 and even on their interactions with the insect. This is especially important when the toxicity
488 by contact is considered, which is especially important when the control of terrestrial or aerial
489 insect pest are considered and hence the evaluation of the spreading and evaporation may
490 present a limited impact on the interaction of the studied emulsions against larvae as result
491 of the aquatic life cycle of *Aedes aegypti* larvae occurs. However, considering that larvae can
492 be found in two possible situations: larvae at the air/water interface or below the surface, it
493 is expected that the formulation will increase its larvicidal activity when the EO droplets wet
494 completely the chitin exoskeleton, thus displacing the water layer. Despite this is an obvious
495 conclusion, it is not easy to establish straightforward methods for the design of the appropriate
496 oil characteristics and the correct surfactant to be used in the formulation. This is because the
497 chemical composition and the topography of the exoskeleton is not uniform. The
498 irregularities of the surface can lead to the pinning of the three-phase contact line as well as
499 to a wetting behavior intermediate between the Cassie-Baxter and the Wenzel scenarios.⁶⁵
500 Therefore, no clear conclusions about the wetting ability of the EO droplets stabilized by the
501 surfactant can be extracted in the absence of a good determination of the topography of the
502 exoskeleton and the building of a model surface with the appropriate chemical and
503 topological characteristics. Therefore, even though the analyzed situation is far from the real
504 situation appearing during the interaction of larvicidal formulations with larvae and the
505 surface used is a very simple hydrophilic surface (silicon wafers with a silicon oxide layer of
506 around 2-3 nm on their surface as was evaluated independently by ellipsometry and neutron
507 reflectometry ⁶⁶) which is far from the composition of the cuticle surface of the insects, ^{67, 68}.
508 the study of the spreading and evaporation processes of microdroplets of the formulations
509 may present a big interest for the optimization of larvicidal formulations. Thus, the evaluation
510 of the time dependences of the droplet contact angles, volumes and radius may help on
511 different aspects related to the optimization of botanical insecticides based on essential oil
512 compound in water emulsions ⁶⁹. Figure 6 shows the time dependences of the contact angle,

513 volume and radius for a set of droplets belonging to different emulsions containing only
514 thymol as oil phase onto the silicon oxide surface.

515 The decrease of the contact angle and volume of the droplets and the increase of their radius
516 with the time may be explained assuming the coupling between the spreading of the droplets
517 on the surface and the evaporation of the water (main component of the studied emulsions)
518 ⁷⁰⁻⁷². The results show similar time dependences for the geometrical parameters,
519 independently of the considered emulsions, only variations of the time scales involved in the
520 spreading/evaporation process and the values of contact angle, volume and radius on the
521 composition of the emulsions are observed from the experimental rate. This may be explained
522 considering that the spreading rate is mainly governed by the oil phase and the copolymer,
523 with the water evaporation, for such diluted emulsions, proceeding with a similar rate than
524 in pure water droplets ⁷². Thus, water evaporation pushes the oil droplets to the proximity of
525 the surface and force their aggregation, with the coalescence and Ostwald ripening rates
526 controlling the spreading process.

527

528 Figure 6. Time dependences for droplet contact angle θ (a), radius L (b) and reduced volume
529 V/V_0 (with V_0 is the volume after deposition of the droplet onto the surface) (c) for emulsions
530 with an oil phase formed by 1 wt% of thymol and different concentrations Pluronic[®] F127.

531

532 The effect of the copolymer concentration is clear from the results in Figure 6, with the
533 emulsions stabilized with the lowest copolymer concentrations having a contact angle closer

534 to that corresponding to the advancing contact angle of a droplet of pure water ($55 \pm 3^\circ$). This
535 contact angle decreases with the concentration of the copolymer. Thus, considering the
536 diluted character of the emulsions, it may be expected that the evaporation rate of water may
537 control the process, and only when the oil droplets remains entrapped within a small aqueous
538 droplet, the oil starts to spread onto the wafer surface driving the formation of an oil film
539 upon the complete evaporation of the water. This spreading of the essential oil is possible
540 due to an adhesion mediated by the copolymer and consequently it should be reduced as the
541 concentration of the copolymer is decreased. This justifies the enhanced spreading found as
542 the copolymer concentration is increased (faster decrease of contact angle). This picture is
543 also supported on the stronger increase of the droplet radius with the copolymer concentration
544 which is an indication of a copolymer mediated adhesion of the oil phase on the surface.
545 Furthermore, the evaporation of the water is slightly reduced with the increase of the
546 copolymer concentration, which can be explained considering an adsorption of part of the
547 copolymer at the water/vapor interface preventing partially the evaporation.

548 Although one of the most important aspects for the optimization of a formulation based on
549 an emulsions is the control of the stabilization process, and their impact on the properties of
550 the formulations, this work tries to analyze the impact of the composition of the oil phase on
551 the toxicity of the formulations. Therefore, it is required analyze the spreading/evaporation
552 for emulsions containing oil phases with different composition because it may impact on their
553 insecticidal activity upon contact with the targeted organism. Figure 7 shows the time
554 dependences of the geometrical parameters of emulsion droplets, with different essential oil
555 blends forming their oil phase (evidenced by the values of x_c), deposited onto a silicon wafers.
556 It is worth mentioning that the time dependences of the geometrical parameters follows the
557 general trend discussed above.

558 The results show that the spreading of the oil phase and the evaporation of the water is
559 enhanced with the introduction of carvacrol in the oil phase. This may be rationalized
560 considering the different nature of thymol and carvacrol. Thus, it may be expected that the
561 presence of thymol within the oil phase lead to the formation of ordered domains of essential

562 oil compound which may limit the diffusion of the molecules contained in the oil phase and
563 consequently slows down the spreading process. This ordered essential oil domains can
564 probably modify also the dynamic of the water within the emulsion droplets, altering the
565 evaporation rate.

566

567 Figure 7. Time dependences for droplet contact angle θ (a), radius L (b) and reduced volume
568 V/V_0 (with V_0 is the volume after deposition of the droplet onto the surface) (c) for emulsions
569 with oil phases containing different essential oil compounds blends and a concentration of
570 Pluronic[®] F127 of 7.5 wt%.

571

572 It is worth recalling that the results concerning to the spreading and evaporation of emulsions
573 droplets are related to their interaction with a hydrophilic surface, which is the opposite
574 situation occurring when the interaction of an insecticide formulation with insects occurs by
575 contact. Thus, it may be expected that the picture found in the application of the here studied
576 emulsions as insecticide may be reversed in relation to the reported above. However, it is
577 clear that the adhesiveness of the polymeric shell impact decisively on the interaction
578 between the formulation and any surface, with the nature of the oil phase playing also a
579 certain role.

580

581 **Conclusions**

582 This work has studied the preparation of essential oil compounds in water emulsions
583 stabilized by an amphiphilic copolymer, Pluronic[®] F127, in which the oil phase is composed
584 by blends of thymol and carvacrol, and their insecticidal activity against *Aedes aegypti*
585 mosquito. The stabilization of the emulsions is strongly dependent on the composition of the
586 pseudo-ternary mixture (water/essential oil/copolymer), with the increase of the
587 compositional ratio between the copolymer concentration and that of the essential enabling
588 the reduction of the average size of the droplets and polydispersity of the emulsions, which
589 results in an enhancement of the stability of the emulsions. Furthermore, the composition of
590 the essential oil blend also plays a very important role on the distribution of the hydrophobic
591 phase within the copolymer shell, with the progressive substitution of thymol for carvacrol
592 resulting in an increase of the amount of essential oil which can be dispersed within the
593 aqueous phase. However, neither the size of the droplets nor the organization of the essential
594 oils within the emulsions present any significant impact on the larvicidal activity of the
595 emulsions against *Aedes aegypti* larvae, with the chemical nature of active ingredient
596 contained within the oil phase, i.e. whether pure essential oil compounds or their blends are
597 used as oil phase, being probably the most critical parameter on the evaluation of the toxicity
598 of this type of formulations. The most effective emulsions against mosquito larvae were
599 found those containing thymol as oil phase, with the introduction of carvacrol resulting in an
600 additive effect on the larvicidal activity on the formulations. Even though the essential oil
601 compound in water emulsions present a strong effect against mosquito larvae, their activity
602 as growth regulators is limited. One of the most critical aspects related to the activity of any
603 insecticidal formulation is their interaction with the insect cuticle, which acts as a barrier for
604 the penetration of the active molecules. This is evaluated in a semi-quantitative way in terms
605 of the spreading of the formulations onto a solid surface, with the results suggesting that the
606 concentration plays an essential role on the control of the interaction of the active compounds
607 (essential oils compounds) and the surface. Furthermore, the results have also evidenced an
608 important role of the chemical nature of the essential oil compounds on the interactions of
609 the formulations with the surface. However, a more appropriate discussion of the correlations
610 between the spreading and evaporation of the formulations and the toxicity will require a

611 careful examination of the characteristic tipping times associated with the interaction of the
612 formulations and mosquito.

613 On the basis of the insecticidal activity of this formulations in relation to synthetic insecticide,
614 and considering the simplicity of the methodology used for their preparation, essential oil in
615 water emulsions should be considered as a promising alternative of the preparation of ready-
616 to-use formulations against insect pest. Furthermore, the high water content of the
617 formulations may facilitate the bioavailability of the active compounds (essential oil), and
618 limit their risks and hazards for human health and non-target organism (plants or animals).
619 Therefore, even though a careful examination of the dose-response of the formulations
620 against *Aedes aegypti* mosquito and of their long-term stability are required for obtaining a
621 formulation with real field application, o/w emulsions containing essential oils are expected
622 to be a promising safe and viable alternative for an eco-sustainable chemical control of insect
623 pest.

624

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631

632 **Contributor roles**

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641 project administration; funding acquisition; resources. **Eduardo Guzmán:**
642 conceptualization; methodology; software; validation; writing—original draft preparation;
643 investigation; writing—review and editing; visualization; funding acquisition.

644

645 **Conflicts of Interest**

646 The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study;
647 in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the
648 decision to publish the results.

649

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876 Essential oil compound in water emulsions are promising alternatives for designing eco-
877 sustainable formulations for controlling *Aedes aegypti* larvae